

another treatment, seeds soaked in water for 24 h were dressed with 1 or 2% NC powder and incubated for 48 h.

Untreated seeds were used for the check.

At 7 d after sowing, individual TN1 seedlings in 15- × 1.5-cm glass test tubes were infested singly with first-instar BPH nymphs. TN1 or IR42 seedlings were infested with first-instar GLH nymphs. Insect survival was recorded daily until all nymphs became adults or died.

Fewer BPH nymphs reached adulthood on TN1 seedlings treated with NSKE or NC than on check seedlings, but only 10% neem extract treatment was significantly more effective than other treatments (Table 1). Only treatment with 10% NSKE reduced GLH nymph emergence on highly susceptible TN1. GLH nymph emergence on IR42 was not significantly affected by neem derivatives, probably because IR42 is already moderately resistant to GLH.

Seed germination of IR36 and IR42 and seedling root length, shoot length, and chlorophyll content were not affected by neem treatment. In fact,

Table 2. Effect of treating rice seed with crude NSKE and NC on germination and seedling vigor.^a IRRI, 1987.

Neem treatment (%)	Germination (%)	Growth index		Length (mm)		Dry wt (mg)/10 seedlings	Chlorophyll ^b (µg/g)
		Root	Shoot	Root	Shoot		
<i>IR36</i>							
NSKE							
2.5	96 a	77.5 a	66.0 a	250.3 a	105.0 a	91 a	51 a
5.0	95 a	79.8 a	71.3 a	249.3 a	104.0 a	92 a	50 a
10.0	94 a	81.5 a	70.5 a	250.8 a	106.0 a	90 a	52 a
NC							
1.0	94 a	60.8 b	60.5 b	249.3 a	106.0 a	90 a	50 a
2.0	96 a	55.0 c	63.5 b	250.0 a	105.8 a	89 ab	51 a
0 (check)	94 a	34.8 d	44.3 c	249.8 a	105.3 a	85 b	49 a
<i>IR42</i>							
NSKE							
2.5	96 a	43.8 ab	46.8 b	218.0 a	80.0 a	83 ab	106 a
5.0	96 a	39.5 b	47.8 b	220.5 a	80.8 a	85 a	106 a
10.0	95 a	48.8 a	52.5 a	219.5 a	80.0 a	84 ab	105 a
NC							
1.0	95 a	24.8 c	22.5 c	220.0 a	80.0 a	80 bc	104 a
2.0	95 a	24.8 c	26.3 c	220.8 a	81.0 a	82 abc	106 a
0 (check)	94 a	16.0 d	17.3 d	219.0 a	81.0 a	78 c	104 a

^a Av of 5 replications. In a column, means for each variety followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b Fresh weight basis.

soaking seed in NSKE increased seedling vigor, with significantly higher seedling root and shoot growth indices than control. NC treatment also improved seedling vigor, but not as

much as NSKE. Dried IR36 and IR42 seedlings germinated from seeds without neem treatment weighed significantly less than seedlings germinated from neem-treated seeds (Table 2). □

Effect of plant derivatives on green leafhopper (GLH) and rice tungro (RTV) transmission

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Leaf extracts of nirgunda *Vitex negunda* L., croton *Crotons sparsiflorus* Marong, bilwa *Aegle marmelos* Coor., ocimum or sweet tulsii *Ocimum sanctum* L., and ikshugandha *Tribulus terrestris* L. in water; seed oils of neem *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss, laural *Calophyllum inophyllum* L., mahua *Madhuca longifolia* Koen. Macbr. var. *latifolia* Roxb. chevai, custard apple *Annona squamosa* Linn. in water emulsified with 1% teepol; crude seed extract of neem and cake extract of neem in water; and insecticides phosphamidon (dimecron)

GLH survival and RTV infection rates on TKM9 seedlings sprayed with leaf extracts, seed oils, and insecticides.

Source	Rate ^a	GLH survival (%)			RTV (%)
		1 d	5 d	10 d	
Leaf extracts					
Nirgunda	10	100	65	15	14
Crotons	10	100	90	30	64
Bilwa	10	100	40	5	26
Ocimum	10	100	65	5	33
Ikshugandha	10	100	60	10	36
Seed oil or extracts					
Neem oil	1	15	0	0	25
Custard apple oil	1	60	0	0	33
Laural	1	60	5	0	39
Mahua	1	80	45	5	17
Neem seed extract	2	95	75	0	54
Neem cake extract	5	100	55	5	31
Insecticides					
Carbofuran 3 G	1.3	7	0	0	29
Phosphamidon	0.1	15	0	0	50
Control		100	90	15	75

^aIn percent, except carbofuran in kg/ha.

and carbofuran were tested for effects on survival of GLH *Nephotettix virescens* Dist. and RTV transmission.

The plant derivatives and insecticides were sprayed on 10-d-old TKM9 seedlings raised in mud pots, using a

baby hand sprayer. Five hours after spraying, the seedlings were removed and the root portion washed.

The seedlings in test tubes with water were exposed for 24 h to GLH that had fed on RTV-infected plants for 4 d, at 2 insects/seedling. Fifty seedlings were inoculated per treatment.

Inoculated seedlings were

transplanted in pots in insect-proof cages for development of symptoms. A fresh seedling already treated with a plant product or chemical was introduced into each tube containing an insect. Survival of insects was recorded until all insects died.

Seed oils gave higher GLH mortality than leaf extracts (see table). Neem oil

gave the highest mortality. GLH mortality on leaf extract-treated seedlings was not significantly different from that on untreated seedlings.

Percentage RTV-infected seedlings was much reduced in all treatments over control. Seedlings treated with leaf extracts of nirgunda and bilwa had low RTV infection rates. □

Weed management

Chemical weed control in transplanted rice

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Two experiments, one in less weedy and one in highly weedy fields, evaluated five herbicides — piperophos + dime-thametryn, butachlor, chlornitrofen, thiobencarb, and pendimethalin — at the adaptive research farm and 5 farmers' fields in 1983. Chlornitrofen and piperophos + dimethametryn were

not used in the highly weedy trials. An unweeded check was maintained.

The experiments were laid out in completely randomized blocks with three replications. KS-282 rice variety seedlings were transplanted at 35-40 d in 10- × 6-m plots the last week of Jun. Butachlor mixed with 60 kg sand and other granular herbicides were broadcast; pendimethalin in 400 liters water/ha was sprayed 2-3 d after transplanting (DT). Water (4-5 cm deep) was retained in the fields for 5 d to allow herbicides to dissolve and make a

layer or film on the soil or water surface. Fertilization was 115 kg N, 25 kg P, and 47.3 kg K/ha. All the P and K and half the N were added at puddling, half the N at 30 DT. Weed count at 45 DT and at tillering (75 DT) was taken from 2 randomly selected 1-m² quadrats/plot. Yields were averaged.

Benefit-to-cost ratios were calculated by dividing the extra benefits attained from enhanced yield by the extra costs incurred for each treatment. Extra costs and benefits included cost and labor charges for herbicide application and price of enhanced yield.

Tillering was enhanced significantly by weed treatments except at the lower rate of butachlor in highly weedy fields (see table). The presence of grassy and more competitive weeds such as *Echinochloa colona* (L.) Link, *E. crus-galli* (L.) Beauv. and *Paspalum distichum* L., resulted in significant yield losses. Weed control was not necessary when weed infestations were low. Weed control in rice can be economically achieved with chemical herbicides. Underdosing of butachlor is not beneficial.

In order of their prevalence, weeds in the experimental fields were *Cyperus iria* L., *C. difformis* L., *C. rotundus* L., *Fimbristylis miliacea* (L.) Vahl, *Echinochloa crus-galli* ssp. *hispidula* (Retz.) Honda, *Sphenoclea zeylanica* Gaertn., *E. colona*, *E. glabrescens* Munro ex Hook. f., *Marsilea minuta* L., *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers., *Paspalum distichum*, *Nymphaea nouchali* Burm. f., *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn., *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* (L.) Willd., *Leptochloa chinensis* (L.) Nees, *Digitaria ciliaris* (Retz.) Koel., and *Trianthema portulacastrum* L. □

Effect of chemical weed control on tillering and yield of transplanted coarse rice and benefit-to-cost ratios of different weeding treatments in less and highly weedy fields.

Herbicide ^a	Dose (kg ai/ha)	Weed control ^b (no./m ²)	Tillering ^b (no./m ²)	Paddy yield ^b (t/ha)	Benefit:cost ^c
<i>Less weedy fields</i>					
Check	—	25.7	e 299.2 a	5.1 a	—
Piperophos + dimethametryn G	0.910	4.0	bc 328.7 ab	5.5 a	—
Butachlor EC	0.975	11.3	d 309.1 ab	5.1 a	—
Butachlor EC	1.200	2.0	a 340.0 b	5.6 a	—
Chlornitrofen G	3.600	15.5	d 305.5 ab	5.1 a	—
Thiobencarb G	2.000	6.0	c 327.3 ab	5.4 a	—
Thiobencarb G	2.500	3.0	ab 337.9 b	5.5 a	—
Pendimethalin EC	1.237	5.0	bc 334.0 ab	5.5 a	—
<i>Highly weedy fields</i>					
Check	—	164.3	e 215.6 a	5.3 a	—
Butachlor EC	0.975	72.0	d 226.2 a	5.6 a	1.82:1
Butachlor EC	1.200	11.7	a 285.6 c	7.5 d	9.79:1
Thiobencarb G	2.000	35.0	c 252.5 b	6.2 b	2.88:1
Thiobencarb G	2.500	22.3	bc 268.1 bc	7.0 c	4.40:1
Pendimethalin EC	1.237	15.3	ab 270.4 bc	7.0 c	4.33:1

^a G = granule, EC = emulsifiable concentrate. ^b Av of 6 sites and 3 replications at each site in the district. In a column, figures followed by a common letter are not statistically different at 0.05% level of confidence (DMRT). ^c For economic analysis, the costs included herbicide price (thiobencarb 10 G @ \$1.21/kg, and butachlor 60 EC and pendimethalin 33 EC @ \$8.62 and \$8.05/liter, respectively) and application costs (\$2.59 or \$1.44/spray or broadcast). Benefits included the price of enhanced yield over that of the check @ \$3.33/140 kg paddy.

Benefit:cost = $\frac{\text{extra benefits}}{\text{extra costs}}$ (for treatments).